

BEHAVIOR OF STITCHED WOVEN S2-GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES UNDER HIGH STRAIN COMPRESSION LOADS

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ABSTRACT

In the current study, investigations were carried out to understand the behavior of stitched/unstitched S2-Glass/SC-15 epoxy composites under high strain rate compression loading using a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar setup. 15 layers of Plain Weave S2-Glass Fabric were used to fabricate stitched/unstitched laminates with low viscosity room temperature curing SC-15 epoxy resin system. For stitching, a 3-cord Kevlar thread was used. Fabric preform was stitched through the thickness in lock-stitch pattern maintaining a pitch of 6 mm. The fabric was stitched along the length and width forming 25.4 mm stitch grid. Four different types of samples were considered. Sample configuration was designated according to the location of stitch line as compared to the loading direction. Dynamic and static responses of the laminate under compression were compared. Failure modes were studied using optical microscopy. For high strain rate loading, samples of dimension 22.5 X 22.5 X 9.5 mm were tested at five different pressure settings of the Hopkinson Bar Setup. Results of the tests were studied in terms of peak stress and the strain at peak stress and the failure modes.

Keywords: VARIM, Hopkinson Pressure Bar, High Strain Rate Loading, Woven Composites, Stitching

INTRODUCTION

In some practical cases, loading on composite structures is dynamic. For example, bird strikes on aircraft structures, underwater mine blasts on ship hulls, ballistic impact on civil structures, armored vehicles, and automobile accidents. Further, development of constitutive equations for the material used in structures subjected to dynamic loading requires the knowledge of the variation in material strength with applied rate of loading and how stress and strain are related. Hence, it is essential to characterize the response of composite materials to high strain rate loading. Studies related to the testing of stitched composites at high strain rates are limited. Much of the previous research in the field of high strain rate loading has been performed on unstitched composites and ductile metallic materials. It is only in the recent past that significant efforts have been made to examine high strain rate properties of more brittle substances such as composites, ceramics, and certain geological materials. A Split Hopkinson's Pressure Bar is widely used to generate high strain rate response data of materials under tension, compression, and torsional loading as it gives the scope to test materials over a wide range of strain rates. In the last two decades, research on the high strain rate response of laminated fiber reinforced composites has gained momentum as these materials are increasingly accepted as viable lightweight structural materials. Sierakowski has reviewed over 120 articles dealing with high strain rate behavior of filamentary composites materials [1]. In this article, various experimental techniques used for evaluating the dynamic performance of composites, as well as results obtained by researchers for various types of filamentary composites, are discussed. El-Habak studied the effect of sizing of the fibers, and two different resin systems: epoxy and vinyl ester [2]. He found that, while sizing did not influence the high strain rate behavior, composites made of vinyl ester matrix yielded higher strength. Montiel et al reported the dynamic behavior of AS4

graphite/PEEK cross-ply composite laminates at strain rate upto 8/s using a drop tower assembly [3]. Results from these studies indicate that at strain rates of the order of 8/s, the strength increased 42% over the static values and strain to failure increased over 25%. Harding studied the effect of strain rate and specimen geometry on the compression strength of woven glass-reinforced epoxy laminates [4]. Results show that the compression strength and failure strains are strongly dependent on the specimen geometry. Researchers at the University of Delaware have studied the dynamic response of a large number of composite material systems up to strain rates of 1200/s and gathered data on the changes in yield stress, yield strain, ultimate stress, modulus of elasticity and total strain energy to failure [5-7] Results of their study indicate considerable increase in strength and stiffness with the increase in strain rate. In general, the high strain response was found to be largely material dependent. Waas et al have studied static and dynamic response of unidirectional glass/epoxy laminates with varying fiber volume fraction [8]. They found that dynamic strength and relative strain are 1.7 times higher than that of the static values. However, they conclude that there is only a marginal difference in the static and dynamic stiffness. Dee et al have investigated the dynamic compressive properties of a uniweave composite laminate with and without reinforcement stitching and have reported that there is a reduction in peak stress value due to stitching [9].

From the literature study, it is evident that work on high strain rate characterization of stitched composites is very limited. Stitching is being considered in the industry for improving the damage resistance/tolerance of composites [11-16]. Hence, in the current work, characterization of stitched woven S2-Glass/epoxy composites under high strain rate compression rate loading is undertaken utilizing a modified SHPB. Stitched and unstitched plain weave laminates were fabricated with 15 layers of Owen Corning's plain weave S2-Glass fabric using affordable liquid molding process, VARIM. 12.7 mm (width) x 12.7 mm (height) x (thickness) samples are prepared from the laminates. Samples were tested at five different pressure settings yielding five different strain rates. For each strain rate, three samples were tested. Peak stress, strain at peak stress are tabulated and compared. Response of sample to loading under static and high strain rate conditions is compared. Failure mechanisms are characterized through optical microscopy.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Fabrication of sample

For both stitched and unstitched configuration, 15-layer S2-Glass/epoxy laminates were manufactured using vacuum assisted resin infusion molding process with Applied Polymeric low viscosity SC-15 resin system. For the fabrication of stitched laminates, layers of dry fabric were stacked together and stitched through the thickness using 3-cord Kevlar thread in a lockstitch pattern with a stitch pitch of 6 mm. Orthogonal grid pattern of stitch was employed. Details of the fabrication are given in ref. 16. Samples of 22.5 X 22.5 X 9.5 mm were cut for the testing. Subsequently, specimens were polished using sanding rotor equipped with fine sandpaper (grit # 800) to ensure parallel loading edges.

Static Compression Testing

To determine the static strength, quasi-static test was carried out on different types of samples used in the study in an M.T.S machine in displacement control mode with a constant crosshead speed of 1.27 mm/min. The load and crosshead displacement response for each test was recorded by the data acquisition system. The data was corrected for machine compliance. For this, a test was carried out without any

sample by loading platens in compression and recording resulting load-displacement response. From this response, the slope of displacement-load was determined, which gives combined compliance of the testing machine and loading platens. Load data for each sample was multiplied by the compliance value giving displacement of the machine and loading platens. The displacement value so determined was deducted from the test data of sample, which gives actual displacement of the sample.

High Strain Rate Testing

For high strain rate testing, a Split Hopkinson's Pressure Bar test system was used on different samples in this study. The setup used consists of striker, incident, transmission bars made of 1045 maraging steel, diameter of which is 38.1 mm. The length of striker bar is 22.86 cm, while that of incident and transmission bars is 1.524 m (60") each. The Specimen is sandwiched between the incident bar and the transmission bar. Petroleum jelly is applied at surfaces of the specimen in contact with the bars to reduce the effect of friction. In using the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar, strain gage transducers mounted on the incident and the transmission bars at a distance of 76.2 cm (30") from the specimen are used as signal monitors. The transient strain history is recorded from the strain gages mounted on the incident and the transmission bars. Two gages are mounted diametrically opposite to each other on each bar to eliminate the recording of any bending strains. The data is acquired using a high-speed data acquisition card with Gagescope V2.92 software at a sampling rate of 2MHz. The stress-strain relation is developed based on one dimensional elastic bar-wave theory for a pulse propagating in a uniform bar, which is initially unstrained and at rest before the pulse arrives. The transient stress and strain rate are given by the relations

$$\sigma_s = E \frac{A}{A_s} \varepsilon_t = K_1 \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_s = \frac{-2C_0}{L} \varepsilon_r = K_2 \varepsilon_r \quad (2)$$

Where ε_r , ε_t , are, respectively, the reflected and transmitted pulses, L is the length of the specimen, E and A are Young's modulus and the cross-sectional area of the Hopkinson's bars respectively, C_0 is the wave velocity in the Hopkinson's bars and A_s is the specimen of cross-sectional area. K_1 and K_2 are the stress and the strain rate multiplying factors for a given specimen and the setup. Hence, only the transient strain data is required to be recorded. Utilizing this data and using equations 1 and 2, the transient stress and strain rate can be calculated. Strain rate data is then integrated to get the strain versus time data. On superimposing with the stress versus time data, the transient stress-strain data is obtained. For this data analysis, VuPoint signal analysis software was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

15-layer stitched and unstitched laminates were fabricated using VARIM process. Samples of size 22.5 X 22.5 X 9.5 mm were tested under static and high strain rate compression loading. For, high strain rate loading, the samples were tested at five different pressure settings yielding five different strain rates. Three samples were tested for each test. For the stitched samples, three different configurations were tested relative to the position of stitch line with respect to the loading direction: 1) cross stitching, 2)

perpendicular to stitch line, and 3) parallel to stitch line as indicated in figure 1. Results of the tests are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Static and high strain rate response of S2-Glass Epoxy composites

Strain Rate	Cross Stitch		Perpendicular to stitch line		Along stitch line		Unstitched	
	Peak Stress (Mpa)	Strain at peak stress	Peak Stress (Mpa)	Strain at peak stress	Peak Stress (Mpa)	Strain at peak stress	Peak Stress (Mpa)	Strain at peak stress
205/s	255	0.0148	212	0.0151	320	0.0225	303	0.0179
	324	0.0168	274	0.0176	250	0.0208	332	0.0172
	267	0.0147	302	0.0165	256	0.0201	341	0.0174
Average	282	0.0154	263	0.0164	275	0.0211	325	0.0175
500/s	278	0.0181	285	0.0186	324	0.0193	329	0.0186
	352	0.0179	344	0.0179	275	0.0190	331	0.0201
	356	0.0185	298	0.0175	341	0.0191	335	0.0189
Average	329	0.0182	309	0.0180	313	0.0191	332	0.0192
671/s	311	0.0216	322	0.0192	345	0.0208	356	0.0195
	377	0.0208	349	0.0206	243	0.0225	402	0.0207
	331	0.0192	287	0.0186	341	0.0232	431	0.0202
Average	340	0.0205	319	0.0195	310	0.0222	396	0.0201
761/s	323	0.0174	355	0.0196	254	0.0194	391	0.0196
	384	0.0178	384	0.0179	329	0.0225	388	0.0199
	361	0.0177	332	0.0173	346	0.0209	439	0.0208
Average	356	0.0176	357	0.0183	310	0.0209	406	0.0201
854/s	321	0.0206	356	0.0177	322	0.0187	405	0.0190
	334	0.0191	320	0.0204	267	0.0187	391	0.0212
	269	0.0196	419	0.0177	392	0.0216	412	0.0204
Average	308	0.0198	365	0.0186	327	0.0197	403	0.0202
Static	140	0.0427	199	0.0376	153	0.0339	170	0.0391
	173	0.0365	216	0.0349	148	0.0321	194	0.0285
	172	0.0403	143	0.0432	159	0.0386	179	0.0275
Average	162	0.0398	186	0.0386	153	0.0349	181	0.0317

Figure 1. a) Unstitched; b) Stitched with 25.4mm spacing : i) Cross stitching; ii) Perpendicular to stitch line; iii) Along stitch line.

Figure 2. Stress- strain curves and optical microscopic pictures for dry cross stitch samples. Dimensions are in mm.

Figure 2 illustrates the stress-strain response of cross stitch laminate loaded in the inplane direction for both static and dynamic loadings. Here, each curve is a representative sample for static and high strain rate loading and is not the average of three samples tested for each case. All dimensions are given in mm. This figure also represents the side view of the optical microscopic images of the impacted samples. From the graph, it is evident that, as the strain rate is increased from 205/sec to 761/sec, the peak stress continues to rise, but the initial slope of the curve increases slightly. But for strain rate above 761/sec (i.e., 854/sec), a reduction in slope of the curve and the peak stress is noted, which indicates that the damage threshold of sample under high strain rate impact loading is attained for strain rates below 854/sec. The peak stress is higher for the dynamic loading case but strain at peak stress is higher for static loading case. The average value of peak stress is 162 MPa for the quasi-static, and 282, 329, 340, 356 and 308 MPa, respectively, for the samples tested at strain rates of 205/s, 500/s, 671/s, 761/s and 854/s. The observed trend is due to the combined effect of the viscoelastic nature of the polymeric matrix, the time dependent nature of the accumulating damage and considerable temperature rise in the sample. To investigate the failure modes, samples were subjected to optical microscopic inspection following the high strain rate tests, which are shown in Figure 2. From Figure 2, at lower strain rates (205/sec-500/sec), samples exhibit shear matrix cracking and fiber micro buckling. But at strain rate (671/s), matrix cracking is visible and fiber micro buckling occurs along the shear fracture surface. Fiber micro buckling was seen to be restricted between the impact face of the sample and stitch location. At higher strain rates (761/sec-854/sec), there is extended fiber micro buckling that coincides with the waviness of the fibers, and the matrix cracks extend from both faces of the sample. Here again, the fiber micro buckling was restricted between stitch and the impact face. Delamination was arrested by the stitch in both sides.

Figure 3. Stress- strain curve and optical microscopic pictures for dry samples-loading direction perpendicular to stitch line.

Figure 3 represents the stress-strain response of samples loaded in the direction perpendicular to the stitch line for both static and dynamic loadings along with the optical micrographs. From the figure, it is seen that, as the strain rate is increased from 205/sec to 761/sec, the peak stress continues to rise, but the initial slope of the curve increases slightly. But for strain rate above 761/sec (i.e., 854/sec), a reduction in the peak stress is noted, which indicates that the damage threshold of the sample under high strain rate impact loading is attained for strain rates past 854/sec. The peak stress for the dynamic loading case is almost 1.4 to 2 times higher than that of static one. The average value of peak stress is 186 MPa for the quasi-static, and 263, 309, 319, 357 and 365 MPa, respectively, for the samples tested at strain rates of 205/s, 500/s, 671/s, 761/s and 854/s. From the optical studies, it is evident that at lower strain rates (205/sec-500/sec), samples exhibit shear matrix cracking. The cracks initiate from the loading face and terminate near the stitch line. But at strain rate 671/sec, this matrix cracking leads to shear fracture as well as fiber micro buckling along the fracture front. Fiber micro buckling was seen to be restricted within the impact face of the sample and stitch location. At strain rate 761/sec, there is a splitting of the laminate. For the sample tested at 854/s, there is a mushrooming effect. Separation of fiber layers started from the impact faces, which got restricted by the stitch line. Here again, the fiber micro buckling was restricted between stitch and the impact face.

Figure 4. Stress- strain curve and optical microscopic pictures for dry samples-loading direction along the stitch line.

Figure 4 illustrates the stress-strain response of laminate loaded in the inplane direction along stitch line for both static and dynamic loadings. This Figure also represents the optical microscopic view of the impacted samples. From the figure, it is seen that as the strain rate is increased from 205/sec to 761/sec, the peak stress as well as initial slope of the curve continues to rise. But for strain rate above 761/sec (i.e., 854/sec), like other categories of stitch samples, a reduction in the slope of the curve and the peak stress are noted, which indicates that the damage threshold of sample under high strain rate impact loading is attained for strain rates past 854/sec. The peak stress is higher for the dynamic loading case. Average

value of peak stress is 153 MPa for the quasi-static, and 275, 313, 310, 310 and 327 MPa, respectively, for the samples tested at strain rates of 205/s, 500/s, 671/s, 761/s and 854/s. The optical microscopic examinations reveal that, at lower strain rates (205/sec), sample does not show any failure at all. At 500/sec, the strain rate sample exhibits shear matrix cracking but at strain rate 671/sec, this matrix cracking is more visible as well as fiber micro buckling. Fiber micro buckling was seen to be restricted within the impact face of the sample and stitch location. At 761/s, shear fracture initiates from the impact face and extends to the other end as longitudinal split. In the case of sample tested at 854/s, the laminate splits into two sub laminates. A total separation of the two sub laminates is, however, prevented by the stitch line.

Figure 5. Stress- strain curve and optical microscopic pictures for dry unstitched samples.

Figure 5 represents the stress-strain response for the unstitched at different strain rates superimposed with static stress-strain curve along with optical micrographs. As the strain rate is increased from 205/sec to 761/sec, the peak stress continues to rise, but the initial slope of the curve increases slightly. But at the strain rate of 854/sec, a reduction in slope of the curve and the peak stress is noted, which indicates that the damage threshold of the sample under high strain rate impact loading is attained for strain rates past 854/sec. The peak stress for the dynamic loading case is almost 50-100 % higher than that of static one. The average value of peak stress is 186 MPa for the quasi-static, and 325, 332, 396, 406 and 403 MPa, respectively, for the samples tested at strain rates of 205/s, 500/s, 671/s, 761/s and 854/s. Peak stress for unstitched samples was comparatively higher than that of stitched samples. To investigate the reasoning for the above happenings, the samples were subjected to optical microscopic inspection following the high strain rate tests. From Figure 5, at lower strain rates (205/sec-500/sec), samples exhibit shear matrix cracking as well as cracks along the length of the sample. But at strain rate of 671/sec, matrix cracking as well as fiber micro buckling and longitudinal splitting become more visible. In addition, there is an evidence of crushing on the impact face. Fiber micro buckling propagated across the length of the sample. At 761/s, in addition to shear cracks, kink band formation, multiple delamination were evident. There is increased crushing on the face in contact with incident bar. At 854/s, in addition to the above failure mechanism, the sub laminate exhibited buckling failure.

CONCLUSIONS

Investigations were carried out on 15 layer stitched/unstitched S2-glass/epoxy for dry and moist laminates under inplane high strain rate compression impact loading using a Split Hopkinson's Pressure Bar Setup. Four categories of stitched/unstitched samples were considered and categorized as per the loading directions: perpendicular to stitch line, along stitch line, cross stitch and unstitched. Three samples of each category were tested at five different strain rates of 205/s, 500/s, 671/s, 761/s and 854/s. Static tests were conducted to compare the results with high strain rate loading. The following conclusions were drawn from the study:

- For all samples the peak stress and slope of the curves increase with the strain rate. But at higher strain rate, a reduction in the peak stress is noted, which indicates that the damage threshold of the sample under high strain rate impact loading is attained
- At lower strain rates, matrix microcracking is the dominant failure mode.
- Under higher strain rates loading, the stitched laminates exhibit a confining effect. The primary mode of failure for unstitched samples is fiber microbuckling with multiple delaminations.
- For stitched samples, fiber microbuckling and micro-delaminations are the major modes of failure and are contained within the bounds of the stitch.

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